

X-Ray Spectral Studies of some Copper(II) Complexes of Schiff Base

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X-Ray K-absorption spectra of one mononuclear and two binuclear tetradentate Schiff base copper(II) complexes have been recorded. The observed edge-shifts, edge-widths and shift of the principal absorption maximum have been correlated with the nature of the bond, ionicity and other structural characteristics of the complexes. The X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) features have been observed in the absorption curves. The small absorption maximum appearing on the low energy side of the main peak A has been assigned the transition $1s \rightarrow 4s^*$. The band gap energies have also been estimated.

The study of X-ray absorption edges and the near-edge structure (XANES) associated with them provides valuable information¹ on the electronic structure and chemical bonding in various types of materials. The study of binuclear copper(II) complexes is attaining importance because their electronic spectra and magnetic properties are interesting and they may provide some models for metallo-enzymes. In the present paper, we report the results of the X-ray spectral studies of some copper(II) complexes of Schiff base. For the present study we have taken one mononuclear complex of Schiff base designated as sample 1. Samples 2 and 3 are binuclear tetradentate Schiff base complexes.

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2

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TABLE 1—CHEMICAL SHIFT, EDGE-WIDTH AND WHITE LINE PARAMETERS OF K-ABSORPTION EDGE OF COPPER IN ITS SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Compd	λ_K -edge ± 0.05 mÅ	E_K eV	Chemical shift ΔE eV	E_A ± 0.05 eV	Edge-width $E_w = (E_A - E_K)$ eV	Shift of the principal absorption maximum eV	White line parameter	
							FWHM ± 0.5 (eV)	p/q
1 (mononuclear)	1 379.70	8 986.4	6.1	9 000.6	14.2	20.3	16.6	0.35
2 (binuclear)	1 379.83	8 985.5	5.2	9 000.8	15.3	20.5	16.1	0.34
3 (binuclear)	1 380.02	8 984.3	4.0	9 002.9	18.6	22.6	15.9	0.29

Energy of copper metal K absorption edge · present work . $E_{K_1} = 8\,980.3$ eV (lit⁹ 8 779.9 eV)

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the copper K-absorption edge for all the three complexes (1–3) studied along with their near-edge structure features. The wavelengths

Fig. 1 Near-edge structure for copper(II) complexes of the Schiff base

and the energies of the K-absorption edges (λ_K, E_K) and the energies of principal absorption maxima (E_A) of copper in the various complexes are given in Table 1. The chemical shifts (in eV) of the K-absorption edge of copper in these complexes with respect to the metal edge are also given in Table 1. For all the complexes, the distances (in eV) of the principal absorption maxima A with respect to the respective K-absorption edges, have also been computed (Table 1). It can be seen that the K-absorption edge of copper is shifted towards the high energy side in all the three complexes as compared to the K-absorption edge in the metal.

Chemical shift : The shift values (Table 1) are 6.1, 5.2 and 4.0 eV for samples 1, 2 and 3 respectively. If we take into consideration the structure of sample 1, the central metal copper ion is surrounded by two oxygens and two nitrogens. The shift value (6.1 eV) is slightly higher for this complex as compared to that for binuclear complexes. In binuclear complexes, as seen from the proposed structure, two copper centres exist. One copper centre is attached to two nitrogens from 2,2'-bipyridyl group and two oxygens from Schiff base ligand. The other copper centre is attached to the same two oxygens from Schiff base ligand, but in this case the copper centre is attached to the nitrogens of Schiff base ligand. Thus we see that oxygens are common to both the copper centres. In this way, their contribution to copper centres is halved as compared to that for the mononuclear complex, thereby reducing the effective charge on the copper centres and resulting in lowering of the chemical shift value in case of the binuclear complexes. Earlier workers² reported the values of chemical shifts for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (6.8 eV); $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5.3 eV), and CuO (4.3 eV) and all these compounds possess the formal oxidation state as +2. A comparison of our values (4.0–6.1 eV) shows that the oxidation state of all the three copper complexes is +2.

Edge-width and shift of the principal absorption maximum : The edge-width values of the complexes follow the sequence : $3 > 2 > 1$. This order establishes that complex 1 is more ionic in character as compared to the complex 2 or 3. This may also be explained in terms of the ligands present

TABLE 2—POSITIONS OF L, L', f AND a, WITH RESPECT TO COPPER METAL K₁ EDGE AND THEIR ENERGY SEPARATIONS FROM THE RESPECTIVE PEAK A (IN eV ± 0.5) IN THE COMPLEXES

Compd	L	L'	f	a	A	L-A	L'-A	A-f	A-a
1	-2.7	2.4	9.6	absent	20.3	23.0	17.9	10.7	-
2	+0.9	5.1	9.3	15.9	20.5	19.6	15.4	11.2	4.6
3	-1.8	1.7	6.5	13.7	22.6	24.4	20.9	16.1	8.9

in the complexes. In complexes 2 and 3 the presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl ligand increases the overall covalent character, thereby increasing the edge-width values as compared to complex 1.

The shift of the principal absorption maximum also follows the trend : 3 > 2 > 1. A similar argument holds in this case also.

Near-edge structure : The positions of the point L where the K-absorption commences, of the small absorption maximum L' on the low-energy side of the main K edge, of the kink f separating the K₁ and K₂ edges, and that of a small absorption maximum (a) on the low-energy side of the main peak (A), with respect to the copper metal K₁ edge position, are given in Table 2.

All the three complexes show white lines. As is evident from the white line measurements (Table 1), the samples under investigation are not ionic but at the same time they are not highly covalent. So, their nature is intermediate. The ratio *p/q* follows the sequence : 1 > 2 > 3, which is also the sequence of relative ionic character of the complexes.

It is important to note that the small absorption maximum (marked as L' in Fig. 1) appearing on the lower energy side of the edge may be assigned the transition *1s* → *3d* empty or partially filled orbitals. In more complex systems, involving π-acceptor ligands, this low energy absorption has

been attributed³ to the transition of a *1s* electron to those anti-bonding MOs that are formed by overlap of filled metal *d_π* orbitals and vacant *p_π* orbitals of the ligands. Similarly, the small absorption maximum marked as "a", appearing on the low-energy side of the principal absorption maximum A, is assigned as a *1s* → *4s** transition^{4,5}.

A perusal of Table 2 shows a marked trend in the variation of various differences reported, i.e. (L-A), (L'-A), (A-f) and (A-a). For all these differences the sequence is 2 < 1 < 3 except for (A-f) difference. The small absorption maximum 'a' is not seen in sample 1. The difference (A-a) for the remaining two samples follows the trend : 2 < 3. Table 3 gives the energy difference between K₁ and K₂ edges, i.e. the difference between *3d* and *4s* levels. Also it gives the difference between *3d* and *4p* levels as well as between *4s* and *4p* energy levels. Interestingly, the band gap of samples 3 and 2 comes out to be the same, i.e. 7.0 eV, whereas the band gap of the mononuclear complex 1 is slightly less (5.6 eV).

Van Nordstrand⁵ investigated the structure of the K-absorption edges of transition metals in a variety of solids and suggested a criterion of coordination symmetry based on the edge structure. Cotton and Hanson⁶ also reported that low energy absorption occurs prominently in the complexes having tetrahedral or lower symmetry, and no such absorption is noticed in octahedral complexes. Sinha

TABLE 3—XANES DATA (IN eV ± 0.5) AT THE K-ABSORPTION EDGE OF COPPER IN THE COMPLEXES

Compd	Component K ₁ <i>1s</i> → <i>3d</i> <i>E_{K1}</i>	Component K ₂ <i>1s</i> → <i>4s</i> <i>E_{K2}</i>	Absorption maximum (A) <i>E_A</i>	<i>E_{K2}</i> - <i>E_{K1}</i> (<i>3d</i> → <i>4s</i>)	<i>E_{K1}</i> - <i>E_A</i> (<i>3d</i> → <i>4p</i>)	<i>E_{K2}</i> - <i>E_A</i> (<i>4s</i> → <i>4p</i>)
1	8 986.4	8 992.0	9 000.6	5.6	14.2	8.6
2	8 985.5	8 992.5	9 000.8	7.0	15.3	8.3
3	8 984.3	8 991.3	9 002.9	7.0	18.6	11.6

and Mande⁷ elaborated the absence of the low energy absorption in case of octahedral complexes. It can be seen from Fig.1 that all the three copper(II) complexes show weak kink in the K-edge which is in conformity of the square-planer structure of these complexes as derived from their magnetic and spectral properties. Earlier workers⁸ also applied the X-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) studies to obtain similar conclusions.

Conclusion : Our results confirm the square-planer geometry of all the three complexes. Further, the relative ionic character of the complexes has been found out. In both the binuclear complexes the appearance of small absorption maximum (a) has been seen and it has been assigned as arising due to $1s \rightarrow 4s^*$ transition. However, such an absorption maximum has not been in mononuclear complex. We have also estimated the band gaps in these materials using the XANES data.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by methods described earlier¹⁰. Sample 1 was prepared by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and 1,3-diaminopropanol. Sample 2 was synthesised by reacting tetradentate Schiff base with copper(bipyridyl)²⁺. Similarly sample 3 was obtained by reaction of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with 1,3-diaminopropanol and copper(bipyridyl)²⁺.

The complexes were characterised by magnetic moment, ir and electronic spectral studies¹⁰.

Sample 1 showed square-planer structure. In samples 2 and 3, the lowering in the magnetic moment values than the expected values, shows that there is a spin-exchange interaction between the two copper(II) centres¹⁰.

The K-absorption spectra of copper in the pure metal and in its complexes were recorded using a 0.4 m Cauchois type bent crystal spectrograph which was equipped with a high quality mica crystal. The (100) planes of mica as the analyser in the first order were used as reflecting planes. The spectra were photographed on Agfa Curix M1 films giving

exposures of the order of 3–5 h for each complex. The absorption screens were prepared by spraying fine powders of the complexes between two cellophane tapes. The optimum thickness of the absorber was determined after several trials and was found to be in the range of 10–15 mg cm⁻². The absorber screen was placed on the window of the X-ray tube in such a way that the entire X-ray beam traversed normally through it. Several microphotometer records of the spectra were taken with a Carl-Zeiss GII microphotometer coupled with a Carl-Zeiss GI BI recorder using magnification 100x.

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